

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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TRANSLATION AS A TEACHING TOOL IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON

Mukhriddin Umaraliyev

*Teacher of the Department of Functional Lexicon of the English Language of Uzbek State
University of World Languages*

[Email:umaraliyevmukhriddin@gmail.com](mailto:umaraliyevmukhriddin@gmail.com)

Mamarayimov Rustam Avazovich

*Secretary of the Department of Functional Lexicon of the English Language of Uzbek State
University of World Languages*

rustamavazovich@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178810>

Abstract. *The article examines the need to use interlingual translation as one of the teaching tools in a foreign language lesson in a comprehensive school. The authors emphasize the urgent need for participants in the educational process to include elements of explanation in their native language and translation exercises in the learning process. The development of translation-oriented exercises should take into account the parameters of the educational communicative situation created in the lesson.*

Keywords: *communicative-functional approach, foreign language lesson, interlingual translation, methodology.*

Interlingual translation performs various functions and is equated to a specific type of speech activity (I. A. Zimnyaya, Yu. V. Ivanova, L. M. Yezhova, etc.). It is obvious that translation is a multifaceted and variable speech activity. That is why the inclusion of interlingual translation in teaching a foreign language raises a large number of problematic questions of a methodological nature, and *the first question* concerns the very concept of "translation" - not as a purely linguistic, but as a psycholinguistic and didactic category. In other words, the question always arises as to what kind of activity and what kind of result from this activity, the teacher requires from students when asking them to translate something from one language to another.

The second question, the answers to which are highly debatable, is whether interlingual translation is needed at all when teaching a foreign language, and if so, should its volume be reduced to a minimum? This question has become especially acute in the last five years since the results of the long-term implementation of translation-free technologies in teaching foreign languages in comprehensive schools in Uzbekistan have not yielded the desired result. We propose to solve the emerging issues concerning interlingual translation from the standpoint of the communicative-

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functional approach, that is, to evaluate the translation within the framework of the communicative situation in which the initiator of the translation, the translating subject and the recipient of the translation are immersed. The communicative-functional approach was formed in translation studies as an alternative to the textual approach and is designed to meet the needs of a specific communicative situation: the translation should be as necessary for specific communicative conditions.

Concerning a foreign language lesson, where the initiator of the translation, the translating subject and the recipient of the translation are the teacher and the student, the communicative-functional approach allows us to treat translation as a necessary element of practicing a communicative situation artificially modeled in the educational environment, as well as a means of teaching and monitoring the assimilation of foreign language material. Accordingly, the lesson should not set the macro-task of creating a full-fledged text in the target language, equivalent to the original in terms of content, meaning, structure and functionality. Educational translation is not aimed at transmitting all the components of the original text. Translation is generally not always regarded as a translation of a text, but merely as a choice of correspondences in another language for units of one language (words, word combinations, sentences). This choice is made by the student or teacher on the basis of already established cognitive experience, according to a translation dictionary and/or context, or involves the operation of retrieving from memory the most suitable or only correspondence in order to ensure the student's precise understanding of the lexical and grammatical meanings of the units of the material being studied, a complete understanding of the content of the statement, and control over the assimilation of the material.

The communicative-functional approach dictates the need to determine to what extent the communicants – the teacher and the student – need interlingual translation in a foreign language lesson. We assumed that the tendency towards non-translational teaching of foreign languages, which has been spreading in Uzbekistan for decades, is effective and there is really no need for interlingual translation in a lesson. We adopted this assumption as a working hypothesis when conducting a survey among teachers and students of secondary schools. The survey was conducted in order to identify: a) the need of participants in the educational process for interlingual translation as a didactic tool in the process of learning a foreign language and b) the place of interlingual translation in the established practice of teaching/learning a foreign language in senior grades of secondary school.

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We are approaching a very complex and acute problem of providing the educational process with methodological materials containing tasks for interlingual translation. The modern line of educational and methodological complexes in the English language almost completely ignores the need and requirement for such tasks. As a result, teachers are overloaded with composing additional assignments, exercises, and assessment materials. Almost all foreign language teachers in comprehensive schools spend extra time composing didactic materials for translation that they can use in class. Providing the educational process with translation exercises would, firstly, relieve teachers who are forced to compose these exercises themselves.

Most of the system of translation assignments can be regarded as a reserve component of the teaching and methodological kit, to which the teacher resorts in case of the need to solve a communicative task through translation or as additional material for individual assignments in class.

Secondly, the developed materials should include criteria for assessing the completion of the assignments "*Translate into English*" or "*Translate into Uzbek*": at the moment, the unsystematic requirements for translations for students are vague, and students often do not understand the task and produce a translation that does not meet the teacher's expectations. It should be noted that students' translations may be adequate, and equivalent, but if they are not performed at the expected level of equivalence [1, pp. 57-58], they do not achieve the set task.

Thirdly, a methodically thought-out system for including translation in the learning process would provide the teacher with a tool for correctly presenting new material using the Uzbek language. Providing the educational process with methodological materials containing tasks for interlingual translation will certainly have a positive effect on foreign language teaching.

Today, non-translation methods lead to the fact that many students often mindlessly "run" the texts of tasks through machine translation and, by analogy, in order to generate their own statements, they first compose them in Uzbek, "run" them through machine translation and rewrite or memorize them with a large number of errors. Even if students have a high level of development of foreign language communicative competence and can independently understand and produce competent speech in a foreign language, working with the semantics of linguistic material remains an extremely important stage of speech activity.

References:

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